

Product III resembled glycine in its resolution factor (0.12), coincidence chromatography, m.p of DNP derivative (201°) and colour reaction with naphthaquinone reagent (greenish purple), ninhydrin (red violet), isatin (brownish purple) and alloxan (purple). The identity of this compound as glycine was further ascertained by the appearance of green colour with o-phthalaldehyde which turned purple on adding urea (.2%) to the reaction mixture and brown on exposure to UV light of 365 m μ . It on ninhydrin mediated oxidative degradation, afforded, like authentic glycine, formaldehyde, which was detected with cromotropic acid. Absorption spectra of both products II and authentic glycine showed λ_{max} 2100.

Product III when deaminated with nitrous acid (10% HCl+5% NaNO₂) in micro capillary tube and the liberated product on oxidation with acid permanganate gave acetaldehyde which gave blue colour with Rimini reagent. One ml of this reagent (10% dimethyl amino-benzaldehyde in HCl) was diluted to four volumes of acetone before use. Being acidic in nature it destroyed the colour produced by ninhydrin and a purple yellow colour was appeared exactly similar to that of authentic α -alanine.

Product V was identified as α -amino-n-butyric acid by its R_f value (0.37), co-chromatography and reaction with ninhydrin (violet) alloxan (purple), Folin's reagent (greenish blue) and isatin (violet blue). Its DNP derivative (m.p. 132°) resembled with that of authentic α -amino-n-butyric acid. Product VI was characterized as valine by the identity of its R_f (0.40), co-chromatography and characteristic colours with ninhydrin (violet), isatin (reddish purple), alloxan (red) and Folin's reagent (bluish green) with that of valine. This product showed bluish white fluorescence under UV black light lamp. Other properties of the products are recorded in Table 1.

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Influence of Some Complexing Agents on the Reactivity of Indian Rock Phosphates

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FROM a study of the action of some complexing agents on the reactivity of various Indian rock phosphates it appears that the complex forming capacity of the agent with the ingredients of the rock phosphates plays a decisive role in releasing more phosphate in solution. The amount of phosphate passing into the solution increases with the lapse of time to a marked extent which may be due to the hydrolysis and subsequent complex formation. The efficiency of phosphate release by complexing agents used varies in the order of EDTA > Oxine > Cupferron > Dimethyl glyoxime. A number of contradictory reports have recently appeared in literature regarding the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates^{1,2}. According to Vaid³ almost all the rich reserves of Rajasthan rock phosphates except only 8% of the Jhamar Kotra rock are less reactive and can not be used without concentration. Hajra and Chakravarti⁴ advocated the use of some chelating agents for increasing the release of phosphates from insoluble iron and aluminium phosphate minerals. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to study the effect of some complexing agents on the reactivity of various rock phosphates so as to ascertain the economic utility of these phosphates available in abundance in different parts of India.

Experimental

Rock phosphates from Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar obtained through Geological Survey of India were powdered, sieved through a 100 mesh sieve (B.S.S.) and analysed in accordance with the procedure described by Washington⁵.

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF DIFFERENT ROCK PHOSPHATES

Ingredients	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
Insoluble material	5.60	7.56	26.05	5.90	17.26	3.24	24.14
Al ₂ O ₃	1.42	23.05	23.92	25.51	33.90	31.26	18.96
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.25	0.32	0.96	12.17
CaO	44.98	32.15	17.00	16.45	15.50	11.38	9.81
MgO	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.35
P ₂ O ₅	27.18	15.46	10.34	30.17	11.97	30.72	15.60

RP=Rajasthan Phosphate, MNP=Mussorie Nodular Phosphorite, MPS=Mussorie Phosphorite Shale, MGP=Mussorie Granular Phosphorite, MVLP=Mussorie Variegated Lenticular Phosphorite, MRP=Mussorie Rock Phosphate, I(B)RP=Itagarh (Bihar) Rock Phosphate.

1 g finely powdered samples of each rock phosphate were treated with 0.1 g EDTA, oxine, cupferron, dimethyl glyoxime and 100 ml distilled water taken in different 250 ml stoppered pyrex conical flasks. After recording the initial pH values, each set was neutralized using either 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH so as to bring pH value at 7. The systems were treated with a few drops of chloroform in order to check fungus growth. The contents of the flasks were stirred daily. Different sets were used for different intervals of time. After definite interval of time the flasks were shaken for half an hour in a mechanical shaker, allowed to stand for some time and then filtered. Aliquot portions were utilized for determining P₂O₅ and pH⁶. P₂O₅ was estimated by the method described by Hajra and Chakravarti⁴. For blank (mineral & water) estimations 1 g powdered samples of each rock phosphate were treated with 100 ml distilled water, few drops of chloroform and kept for 7 days. The results are tabulated.

Results and Discussion

The analysis shows that all the rock phosphates contain appreciable amounts of P₂O₅, calcium, magnesium and iron, suitable for healthy plant growth. It is interesting to note that all the phosphates are alkaline in nature.

It can be reckoned from the Table 2 that the release of P₂O₅ from rock phosphates by water is not much and when complexing agents are used the release increases to a marked extent. On addition of EDTA/Oxine for each system there is a slight lowering of pH at the initial stage but on prolonged incubation pH values tend to return to the original level. This is due to the liberation of H⁺ ions in the medium as a result of the instantaneous interaction between the metal ions of the rock phosphates and EDTA/Oxine. However,

with the lapse of time hydrolysis of the remaining uncombined rock phosphates occur resulting in the rise of pH values of the systems. With other complexing agents the pH values of the systems increase at the initial stage. This may be due to the fact that there is not much complex formation reactions with these agents and a slight increase in pH values at the initial stage occurs on account of hydrolysis of rock phosphates. Further increase in pH values in all the systems with the lapse of time is due to the hydrolysis of rock phosphates.

Thus complexing agents help to decompose the rock phosphates in the initial stage and once the decomposition starts it is followed by the hydrolysis of the remaining rock phosphates which continues with the lapse of time releasing more P₂O₅ in the solution. The degree of decomposing influence of the complexing

TABLE 2(a)—BLANK (MINERAL & WATER) ESTIMATION

Phosphates	pH		P ₂ O ₅ (g/g of the phosphate)	
	Initial	After 7 days	Initial	After 7 days
RP	7.20	7.60	0.48 × 10 ⁻³	0.50 × 10 ⁻³
MNP	7.15	7.55	0.40	0.40
MPS	7.05	7.35	0.10	0.08
MGP	7.05	7.30	0.38	0.32
MVLP	7.10	7.30	0.08	0.10
MRP	7.05	7.25	0.30	0.30
I(B)RP	7.10	7.30	0.22	0.20

TABLE 2(b) — INFLUENCE OF COMPLEXING AGENTS ON THE REACTIVITY OF VARIOUS ROCK PHOSPHATES

Period	Phosphate	EDTA		Oxine		Cupferron		Dimethyl glyoxime	
		pH	P ₂ O ₅ (g/g)	pH	P ₂ O ₅ (g/g)	pH	P ₂ O ₅ (g/g)	pH	P ₂ O ₅ (g/g)
Initial Stage	RP	6.40	0.60 × 10 ⁻³	6.80	0.58 × 10 ⁻³	7.25	0.54 × 10 ⁻³	7.25	0.52 × 10 ⁻³
	MNP	6.40	0.54 "	6.55	0.52 "	7.20	0.48 "	7.20	0.46 "
	MPS	6.45	0.16 "	6.45	0.14 "	7.10	0.14 "	7.10	0.12 "
	MGP	6.45	0.42 "	6.40	0.40 "	7.10	0.38 "	7.10	0.36 "
	MVLP	6.50	0.16 "	6.30	0.48 "	7.15	0.12 "	7.15	0.10 "
	MRP	6.50	0.36 "	6.30	0.38 "	7.10	0.34 "	7.10	0.32 "
	I(B)RP	6.60	0.28 "	6.40	0.30 "	7.15	0.26 "	7.15	0.24 "
After 24 hours	RP	7.40	0.94 × 10 ⁻³	7.35	0.88 × 10 ⁻³	7.30	0.82 × 10 ⁻³	7.30	0.78 × 10 ⁻³
	MNP	7.35	0.86 "	7.30	0.80 "	7.25	0.74 "	7.25	0.70 "
	MPS	7.25	0.28 "	7.20	0.22 "	7.15	0.20 "	7.15	0.18 "
	MGP	7.25	0.68 "	7.20	0.62 "	7.15	0.58 "	7.15	0.60 "
	MVLP	7.30	0.30 "	7.25	0.74 "	7.20	0.20 "	7.20	0.16 "
	MRP	7.25	0.58 "	7.20	0.60 "	7.15	0.52 "	7.15	0.48 "
	I(B) RP	7.30	0.46 "	7.25	0.48 "	7.20	0.40 "	7.20	0.36 "
After 3 days	RP	7.60	0.30 × 10 ⁻³	7.50	0.27 × 10 ⁻³	7.45	0.24 × 10 ⁻³	7.40	0.22 × 10 ⁻³
	MNP	7.55	0.27 "	7.45	0.24 "	7.40	0.21 "	7.35	0.20 "
	MPS	7.45	0.08 "	7.35	0.06 "	7.30	0.04 "	7.25	0.04 "
	MGP	7.45	0.20 "	7.35	0.18 "	7.30	0.18 "	7.25	0.16 "
	MVLP	7.50	0.08 "	7.40	0.22 "	7.35	0.06 "	7.30	0.06 "
	MRP	7.45	0.18 "	7.35	0.20 "	7.30	0.16 "	7.25	0.16 "
	I(B)RP	7.50	0.14 "	7.35	0.16 "	7.30	0.12 "	7.25	0.10 "
After 7 days	RP	7.85	0.70 × 10 ⁻³	7.80	0.64 × 10 ⁻³	7.75	0.56 × 10 ⁻³	7.70	0.64 × 10 ⁻³
	MNP	7.75	0.60 "	7.70	0.56 "	7.65	0.48 "	7.60	0.46 "
	MPS	7.65	0.21 "	7.60	0.16 "	7.50	0.14 "	7.45	0.12 "
	MGP	7.60	0.48 "	7.55	0.42 "	7.45	0.40 "	7.40	0.38 "
	MVLP	7.65	0.22 "	7.60	0.48 "	7.55	0.14 "	7.50	0.12 "
	MRP	7.60	0.42 "	7.55	0.44 "	7.50	0.36 "	7.45	0.34 "
	I(B)RP	7.55	0.35 "	7.50	0.36 "	7.45	0.28 "	7.40	0.22 "

agents used varies in the order of EDTA > Oxine > Cupferron > Dimethyl glyoxime. This may be due to the fact that the rock phosphates contain more calcium than other ingredients like aluminium, iron and magnesium.

This investigation clearly reveals that the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates increases in presence of complexing agents. As metal chelates are better source of micronutrient supply to plants^{7,8,9} rock phosphates with a small quantity of complexing agents are very useful for supplying micronutrient elements and phosphorus to plants.

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Composition of Essential oil of *Elsholtzia strobilifera* Benth

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ELSHOLTZIA strobilifera Benth (N. O. Labiatae), a medicinal-aromatic species, possesses high content of essential oil. The oil has been found to possess antibacterial and antifungal properties^{1,2}. The light yellow coloured essential oil from the fresh plant material was extracted by steam distillation in 0.4% yield. The essential oil was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the physico-chemical properties determined by the conventional methods are: specific gravity = 0.9096/20°, ref. index = 1.4890/20°, sp. rota-

tion = + 4.1, acid value = 0.64, ester value = 13.79, ester value after acetylation = 49.9 and carbonyl value = 49.3.

The essential oil (100 ml) was first separated into hydrocarbon and oxygenated fractions by column chromatography⁴. These were then subjected to fractional distillation under reduced pressure (4-5 mm). Each fraction was purified by column chromatography using silica gel BDH (60-120 mesh) as adsorbent. Purity of the fractions was ascertained by TLC over silica gel coated plates in different solvent systems. In all eleven fractions were obtained and out of these 10 compounds were identified by preparing their characteristic derivatives⁵. The presence of β -pinene, α -phellandrene, dipentene, bisabolene, 1, 8-cineole, linalool, terpinen-4-ol, carvone, citronellol and geranyl acetate was established.

The major fraction (38%) gave tests for a keto compound (2,4-DNP, m.p. 146°). The IR spectrum gave strong bands at 3000, 2960-2910, 1720 and 1640 cm^{-1} , medium intensity bands at 1480, 1400, 1380, 1346, 1300, and 1070 cm^{-1} and weak bands at 840 and 610 cm^{-1} . The mass spectrum of the compound ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$) gave molecular ion peak at $m/e = 152$, the base peak at 55 and other prominent peaks at 40, 95, 83, 69 and 41. The structure is yet to be established with the help of PMR and C^{13} NMR.

TABLE—GLC OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *Elsholtzia strobilifera*

Peak No.	Relative retention time (dipentene=1)	Percentage in the oil	Compound identified
1	0.3	0.55	α -pinene
2	0.4	12.14	β -pinene
3	0.7	0.5	myrcene
4	0.8	1.8	α -phellandrene
5	1.0	10.4	dipentene
6	1.4	5.5	1,8-cineole
7	1.6	trace	γ -terpinene
8	1.8	0.15	<i>p</i> -cymene
9	2.5	1.9	linalool
10	3.0	trace	linalyl acetate
11	3.4	trace	bornyl acetate
12	4.2	trace	unidentified
13	4.4	3.5	terpinen-4-ol
14	4.8	10.5	carvone
15	5.0	38.0	unidentified ketone
16	6.0	4.8	bisabolene
17	6.6	4.4	citronellol
18	7.0	4.4	geranyl acetate